
The Anterior Longitudinal Ligament Ossification in Vertebral Spine in Pakistani Population

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Abstract

Background: The vertebrae are aligned and joined together by intervertebral joints and ligaments in a vertebral column. The anterior longitudinal ligament is one of the most important ligaments, studied widely in context of anatomy. The deterioration of anterior longitudinal ligament can result in various disorders, which includes instability to spine, backache deformities and nerve entrapments.

Objectives: To assess the anterior longitudinal ligament by evaluating the incidence of ossification types along with the associated factors.

Methodology: The study took place from Nov 2020 to March 2021 at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore. It included 20 disarticulated sets of bones and 20 cadavers used in dissection.

Results: Ossification was evident in 3 sets of vertebrae at different levels. On the other hand, cadaveric specimens showed no ossification.

Conclusion: It can be concluded that ossification of anterior ligaments of spine is rare and preventable. By assessing the cause of ossification and preventing it timely, deformities and neurological disorders can be avoided.

Keywords

Anterior Longitudinal Ligament, Vertebral Spine, Ossification

1. INTRODUCTION

The vertebrae are linked with each other to form vertebral column. These are attached strongly through joints and ligaments (Bently & Rieyaz 2019). Among these ligaments, anterior and posterior longitudinal ligaments are responsible for proper alignment of vertebrae. Moreover, these ligaments keep check on displacement of vertebrae on each other (Kim et al. 2004).

The anterior longitudinal ligament extends from second cervical vertebra to sacrum. It is present as a flat and strong band that moves along the anterior side of vertebral bodies. Its thickest part lies in thoracic region (Malik & Soni 2014). It is known for providing stability to the spine. On the other hand, posterior longitudinal ligament extends from axis and continue to sacrum by moving along posterior side of vertebral bodies. At the time of

ossification or calcification in these ligaments, the posture and gait is disturbed due to de-alignment of vertebrae (Belanger & Rowe 2001).

Ossification is a pathologic condition that comprises of heterotropic ossification of spinal ligaments (Benjamin et al. 2006). It can lead towards spinal cord compression and spinal stenosis, resulting in neurological symptoms. However, majority of individuals remain asymptomatic as lesions are usually small (Mizuno & Nakagawa 2001).

The diffuse idiopathic skeletal hyperostosis (DISH), also known as Forestier's disease, is a well known disease (Miyazawa & Akiyama 2007). It comprises of ossification that occurs in ligaments of body. The anterior longitudinal ligament of spine is the most important ligament involved in this disease. It occurs mostly in males with age more than 60 years (Khalid et al. 2000). The prevalence in elderly people is 15-20%. Although it is mostly asymptomatic, the other diseases associated with DISH are clinically detectable (Talijanovic et al. 2009). This includes dyspnea, peripheral nerve entrapment, spinal cord compression and dysphagia. Apart from this, the digestive tract and airway pathway are highly affected by the disease, causing difficulty in swallowing and respiratory issues (Westerveld et al. 2008).

2. METHODOLOGY

The present prospective study was conducted at Jinnah Hospital Lahore from Nov 2020 to March 2021. It included 20 dry bony sets and 20 human cadavers under dissection. The dry bones were assessed for ossifications of ligament remnants by checking margins of lamina and body of vertebrae. The anterior longitudinal ligaments were visualized and palpated for texture change in cadavers, in order to assess presence of ossification.

3. RESULTS

In case of cadaveric specimens, no ossification or calcification was found. The spinal ligaments appeared completely normal at both the inspection and deep palpation. However, in case of dry bone sets, ossification of ligaments was highly evident. This was true for the cervical vertebrae. Out of 3 sets of vertebrae, 2 showed ossification at segmental and continuous levels. On the other hand, 1 set depicted ossification at lumbar level. For ligament with segmental ossification, complete vertebral body was involved with intact disc space lying intervertebrally. However, in case of continuous type, no disc space was involved. Some of the segments also depicted fusion of costotransverse and costovertebral joints. This resulted in ossification of supraspinous ligaments.

3.1 DISCUSSION

DISH is a well-known disease, though reported and recognized a few years back. It has been given different names in literature. The term 'Moniliform Hyperstosis was introduced initially, which later came to known as 'Senile Ankylosing Vertebral

Hyperstosis'. The term 'Diffuse Idiopathic Skeletal Hyperstosis' has recently been used for calcification of anterior longitudinal ligament (Standerling 2008).

In normal conditions, anterior longitudinal fibres are attached to intervertebral disc, margins of near vertebrae and hyaline cartilage end plates. Loose attachment is present with intermediate level of bodies. The fibers are blended at different levels with periosteum perichondrium and peripheral part of annulus fibrosus (Pappone et al. 2005). In DISH, ossification of joint capsule insertions, tendons, ligaments and spine occurs. Mostly the thoracic region of spine is affected adversely. The ossified anterior longitudinal ligament looks like candle wax dripping down the spine (Sar et al. 2018).

The DISH has been reported with high prevalence in various parts of world. This study showed prevalence of 7.5%, which is lower than those reported in previous studies. Bently and Rieyaz (2019) reported prevalence of 9% in India, whereas, Kim et al (2004) reported 2.9% prevalence in Korea. Westerveld (2008) has claimed that DISH is more prevalent in males as compared to females. This is in accordance with the results of present study. All the specimens belonged to male gender. However, no ossification was reported in cadaveric specimens.

The ossification was found in thoracic vertebrae with lumbar vertebral involvement in present study. This is justified under the work of Malik et al (2014), which claimed that thoracic region is highly prone to ossification. According to Talijanovic et al (2009), T7 to T11 are the most affected thoracic vertebrae. In this study, 2 specimens were found with bilateral ossification. In first specimen, left extension was from T8 to T11 and right extension was from T9 to T10. On the other hand, the second specimen showed left extension from T7 to T12 and right extension from T7 to T11. The higher prevalence of ossification in thoracic region has been explained by Mallashetty et al (2013). According to which, the descending thoracic aorta on left side is responsible.

The present study reports ossification in 3 dry bones including 2 at thoracic level and 1 at lumbar level. Similar findings have been reported by Kosuri et al (2014) and Bently and Rieyaz (2019). Kosuri et al (2014) explained that ossification can result in restrictive respiratory movements, both active and passive. This further leads towards pulmonary disorders.

On the basis of ossifications types, segmental type has been the most widely reported one (Kosuri et al 2014). However, in present study no mixed type was seen, whereas, segmental and continuous types were observed equally. Apart from this, supraspinous ligaments were also observed to be ossified. Similar findings have been reported by Bently and Rieyaz (2019). The ossification of anterior longitudinal ligament is affiliated with pyrophosphate metabolic disorder and hypercalcemia disorder.

4. CONCLUSION

The vertebral column is meant to provide stability and flexibility to the spine through alignment of vertebrae, ligaments and joints. The ossified ligaments can deteriorate the functions and arrangement of vertebrae. This can result in improper spine movements. DISH is a well known disorder with ossified anterior longitudinal ligament. The disorder comprises of dysphagia, low backache odynophagia and bracial plexus compression. Resultantly, acute spinal fracture can take place. Despite the importance of the DISH, it is rarely been diagnosed due to ambiguous symptoms.

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